

MEDICAL SCIENCES

RECURRENT UNDIFFERENTIATED PLEOMORPHIC SARCOMA

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ABSTRACT

We report the case of a 50-year-old man who was admitted to the surgical department of the Svilengrad General Hospital in 2019 for surgical treatment of a painless subcutaneous nodule on the dorsal surface of the left forearm. The removed formation was soft, movable, with a macroscopic appearance of a lipoma. A malignant mixed mesenchymal tumor with dominant liposarcoma and epithelioid variant of rhabdomyosarcoma components was diagnosed by biopsy. Two years later, the patient was admitted to KASPELA University Hospital Plovdiv with the same complaints. During the biopsy, the tumor presented as a malignant undifferentiated blastoma, with necrotic areas, brown pigment and marked cellular polymorphism. In the performed IHC study, the tumor immunophenotype was identified as an undifferentiated pleomorphic sarcoma.

Keywords: unclassified sarcoma, undifferentiated pleomorphic sarcoma.

Introduction

The undifferentiated pleomorphic sarcoma, formerly known as malignant fibrous histiocytoma, is a high-grade aggressive soft-tissue sarcoma. Mesenchymal stem cells are the most likely origin of the tumor, instead of histiocytes as previously thought. It can affect soft tissues, retroperitoneum and metastasize to several organs [3].

Undifferentiated soft tissue sarcomas can be divided into four morphologic subgroups: pleomorphic, spindle cell, round cell and epithelioid undifferentiated sarcomas [1]. Pleomorphism in tumors denotes the marked variation in size and shape of tumor nuclei, including prominent nuclear hyperchromasia and irregularities of the nuclear membrane. Typically, pleomorphism corresponds to high-grade aggressive behavior in a neoplasm, but this is not always the case; many benign tumors (e.g. pleomorphic lipoma and atypical fibrous histiocytoma) can also exhibit pleomorphism, and therefore assessment of malignant potential depends on a synthesis of factors including the clinicopathologic context, and other morphologic features such as the mitotic index, and presence of atypical mitoses and tumor necrosis [6, 8].

Pleomorphic liposarcoma is a high-grade pleomorphic sarcoma containing variable numbers of pleomorphic lipoblasts; it lacks any areas of well-differentiated liposarcoma or other lines of differentiation. These tumors most frequently affect older patients,

with a peak in the 7th decade and a slight male predominance. There is a predilection for extremity deep soft tissues, especially the lower limb, but these can occur at a variety of sites, including the trunk and spermatic cord [2].

The pleomorphic sarcoma is a diagnosis of exclusion, where generous sampling of the specimen is required to rule out dedifferentiated tumor or specific differentiation, other than fibroblasts, myofibroblasts and histiocyte-like cells.

Material and methods

The histologic specimens were made with fixation of 10% neutral formalin and embedded in paraffin. The cut sections were 4 mkm thick and stained with hematoxylin and eosin (HE). Immunohistochemical tests for Vimentin, Ki-67, SMA, S-100, HMB-45, Melan A и PAX-8 were performed.

Results

The patient's first surgery was performed in the Surgical Department of Svilengrad General Hospital. The removed subcutaneous formation from the left forearm measured 4.5 x 5.5 cm and had a macroscopic appearance of a lipoma. The biopsy diagnosis of the routine histological examination was a malignant mixed mesenchymal tumor, with dominant liposarcoma and epithelioid variant of rhabdomyosarcoma components (Fig.1). The degree of surgical excision cannot be estimated (BN№241-242/2019)

Malignant mixed mesenchymal tumor - magn.x40, (Fig.1)

Two years later, the patient was admitted with a relapse to "Kaspela" University hospital Plovdiv. The tumor formation had dimensions of 3.5 x 4.5 x 3 cm, yellow-whitish cut surface and smooth periphery. Histologically, the tumor appeared as a malignant undifferentiated blastoma, with extensive necrotic areas and marked cellular polymorphism (Fig. 2,3).

Malignant undifferentiated blastoma with mucoid areas - magn.x40, (Fig. 2)

Malignant undifferentiated blastoma with fibrillar structures and areas of hyalinization - magn.x40, (Fig. 3)

Due to the presence of brown pigment in some tumor cells and evidence of surgically removed carcinoma of the thyroid gland (10 years ago), IHC examination was performed. The immunohistochemical tests showed positive staining for Vimentin (Fig. 4), high proliferative index: Ki-67 - 90% (Fig. 5) and negative expression of SMA, S-100, HMB-45, Melan A and PAX-8.

Malignant undifferentiated blastoma - positive staining for Vimentin - magn.x40, (Fig.4)

Malignant undifferentiated blastoma - high proliferative index (Ki-67 – 90 %) - magn.x40, (Fig.5)

Discussion

The undifferentiated pleomorphic sarcoma, formerly known as malignant fibrous histiocytoma, is a high-grade soft-tissue sarcoma. These tumours are composed of heterogeneous populations of cells with mesenchymal features that can originate from simple genomic alterations or complex genomics [9]. Under light microscopy, undifferentiated pleomorphic sarcoma exhibits atypical, pleomorphic spindle cells with abundant mitotic figures. The depth of penetration can extend through the deep dermis, hypodermis, fascia, and striated muscle. The tumor may display a storiform, fascicular, or sheet-like configuration within a fibrous stroma [7]. The definitive diagnosis of undifferentiated pleomorphic sarcoma is confirmed by excluding other malignancies with a panel of immunohistochemical markers [5]. These should include keratins, S100 protein and/or SOX10; smooth muscle actin (SMA); and desmin, expressed in metastatic sarcomatoid carcinoma, melanoma, and pleomorphic myogenic sarcomas, respectively [4].

Conclusion

Based on the morphological and immunohistochemical characteristics of the tumor, we concluded that this is a case of unclassified sarcoma. The undifferentiated pleomorphic sarcoma is a diagnosis of exclusion, where a generous sampling of the specimen is required to rule out dedifferentiated tumor or specific differentiation, other than fibroblasts, myofibroblasts and histiocyte-like cells.

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